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**NOVEL BIOINSPIRED COMPOSITES FABRICATED BY
ROBOCASTING FOR DENTAL APPLICATIONS**

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4 **Abstract**
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8 Ceramic/polymer dental composites inspired on the microstructure of human
9 enamel are produced by robocasting combined with polymer infiltration. Robocasting is
10 first used to additively manufacture a network of interconnected hydroxyapatite (HAp)
11 rods aligned perpendicular to the occlusal surface, mimicking the natural material. A co-
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continuous composite is then obtained by immersing the sintered ceramic skeleton in an epoxy resin bath that is subsequently cured. The mechanical performance of the resulting bioinspired composite was evaluated through biaxial bending and sliding-wear tests. The results obtained are compared with those of two commercial dental composites. Despite being a first prototype, the bioinspired material exhibited mechanical properties very close, both in terms of **biaxial strength (63 ± 4 MPa)** and wear resistance (**specific wear rate $(7 \pm 2) \cdot 10^{-5}$ mm³/Nm**), to the commercial solutions. The proposed ground-breaking strategy appears, then, as a very promising alternative for the production of innovative dental composites with near-net shape and improved durability.

Keywords: Bioinspired materials; Dental composites; Strength; Wear; Direct Ink Writing

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5 **1. Introduction**
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9 Modern materials for dental prostheses need to balance mechanical properties,
10 durability and aesthetics. Currently available commercial options that fulfil clinical
11 requirements include dental zirconias and biphasic materials such as glass-ceramics
12 (feldspathic porcelain, lithium disilicate, *etc.*) and polymer-ceramic composites [1-4].
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18 Dental zirconias present the best combination of mechanical properties and wear
19 resistance [5, 6] but typically lack the aesthetics (*i.e.*, translucency) of natural teeth.
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21 Moreover, the hardness of zirconia is significantly higher than that of human enamel,
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23 which may pose a risk to opposing dentition, for example by causing antagonist wear [7,
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8] . Biphasic dental materials possess satisfactory aesthetics, but worse mechanical
properties and wear resistance than zirconias. Compared to natural enamel, biphasic
materials can show better single-valued mechanical properties (hardness, strength,
toughness) [9], but lack the complex microstructural features which confer enamel its
remarkable damage tolerance and durability [10].

Common microstructures observed in current dental composites include: (i) a
connected ceramic preform infiltrated by polymer (*e.g.*, Enamic® by Vita [11]), and (ii) a
high load of small, equiaxed, ceramic particles embedded in a polymer matrix (*e.g.*,
Lava™ Ultimate by 3M™ [12]). Although natural enamel can also be regarded as a
biphasic material, its microstructure differs significantly from commercial products: it
consists of tightly packed, mineral rods of high aspect ratio, running from the dentin-
enamel junction to the occlusal surface, separated by softer sheaths with a lower mineral
content. Critically, enamel rods are aligned perpendicular to the occlusal surface in the

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4 external region [10, 13], and intertwined at different angles (known as decussation) in the
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6 region closer to the dentin.
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9 As a result of its microstructure, enamel presents toughening mechanisms both
10 behind (bridging) and ahead of the crack tip (microcracking, branching), and shows R-
11 curve behaviour [13, 14]. The enamel microstructure is also responsible for a
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13 significantly higher wear resistance compared to both dental composites and glass-
14 ceramics, as rods aligned perpendicular to the occlusal surface are more difficult to
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16 detach [15, 16].
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23 Further improvements of the ‘aesthetic’, biphasic dental materials (glass-
24 ceramics, composites) should be aimed at increasing their strength and toughness, as well
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26 as improving their poor wear resistance. One possibility that has not been explored in
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28 depth is that of bioinspired design, *i.e.*, engineering the microstructure to be similar to
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30 that of natural enamel. This is largely because conventional processing techniques cannot
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32 produce the complex features of the enamel structure. However, the advent of advanced
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34 solid free-form fabrication (SFF) techniques opens the door to the development of such
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36 materials, especially biomimetic polymer-ceramic composites [17-19].
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43 Based on the above, the present paper is aimed at exploring the development of
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45 bioinspired composite materials for dental applications using one of the most popular **and**
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47 **successful** SFF techniques for the additive fabrication of ceramics structures: robocasting
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49 or Direct Ink Writing (DIW). **Indeed, robocasting is capable of reproducibly manufacture**
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51 **complex ceramic structures from stable concentrated slurries of all kinds of ceramic**
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53 **powders, with sizes ranging from nanometric to micrometric.** Here, an open
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55 hydroxyapatite (HAp) rod network is printed and subsequently infiltrated by a
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4 biocompatible polymer to produce an array of ceramic rods perpendicular to the occlusal
5 surface (as in enamel), with a small number of transverse rods for structural integrity. To
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7 show the feasibility of this approach, the immediate aim is to demonstrate that even this
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9 basic architecture can achieve fracture strength and wear resistance comparable to those
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11 of current, commercial dental composites. The former is a measure of the resistance to
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13 failure upon single-cycle overloads, and the latter can be used as a proxy of resistance to
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15 long-term, mechanical degradation. The results obtained are discussed with a view at
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17 developing novel dental materials in the immediate future, with improved mechanical
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19 behaviour and aesthetics.
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28 **2. Materials and methods**

29 **2.1 Fabrication of samples**

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33 Commercially available resin-ceramic materials Vita Enamic® (Vita Zahnfabrik,
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35 Bad Säckingen, Germany) and 3M™ Lava™ Ultimate (3M ESPE AG, Seefeld,
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37 Germany), widely employed as prosthetic dental materials, were selected to compare
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39 with the developed bioinspired material and provide a benchmark for fracture strength
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41 and wear resistance. The bioinspired materials were fabricated as hybrid scaffolds of
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43 hydroxyapatite impregnated with epoxy. For that purpose, a water-based slurry for direct
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45 ink writing of scaffolds was prepared from uncalcined hydroxyapatite (HAp) powder
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47 (Captal® 'R', Plasma Biotol Ltd., United Kingdom) with a solid loading of 25 vol.%.
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49 This powder was progressively added to an aqueous solution containing an appropriate
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51 concentration of dispersant (Darvan® C, Vanderbilt Minerals LLD, USA), 10 wt.%
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53 relative to the ceramic powder. Alumina balls were added during the mixing step to break
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4 agglomerates and facilitate the homogenization. Then, hydroxypropyl methylcellulose
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6 (MC) (Methocel F4M; Dow Chemical, USA) was added to the mixture to avoid
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8 segregation by increasing the viscosity of the slurry. Eventually, the ink was jellified by
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10 adding polyethylenimine (PEI, 4 vol.% relative to the liquid content). After adding each
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12 component, the dispersion was homogenized in a planetary centrifugal mixing device
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14 (ARE-250, Thinky, Japan) for 20 seconds at 2000 revolutions per minute.
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19 Regarding the printing procedure, a log-pile pattern of ceramic rods was produced
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21 using a robotic deposition device (3-D Inks, Stillwater, OK) following the computer-
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23 aided model shown in Figure 1, designed in the robocasting software (Robocad 4.9, 3-D
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25 Inks). The slurry was extruded through a cylindrical nozzle (Nordson EFD, Westlake,
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27 OH) with a diameter $d = 0.330$ mm, at a printing speed of 30 mm per second. Each layer
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29 was designed as a pattern of parallel rods oriented with center-to-center separation $s_1 =$
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31 0.7 mm in the odd layers and $s_2 = 1.5$ mm in the even layers. Adjacent rod layers were
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33 orthogonal and the separation between layers, $h = 0.256$ mm, was selected to produce a
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35 20 % overlapping that facilitates printing and ensures good adhesion between layers.
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37 Besides, rods in odd layers were alternatively offset by 50 % of their in-plane separation,
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39 s_1 , as shown in Fig. 1. This design sought to mimic the microstructure of occlusal enamel,
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41 by achieving a small distance between parallel rods in the occlusal surface with a
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43 minimal number of transverse rods that ensure structural integrity. The spacings were not
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45 reduced further to ensure a proper penetration of the polymer in the innermost
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47 macropores of the relatively large scaffolds fabricated, whose external dimensions were
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49 set at $25 \times 25 \times 25$ mm.
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4 The printed scaffolds were dried for 24 h and consolidated in a conventional
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6 furnace at 1200° C for 2 h under a heating ramp of 3° C/min, with an intermediate
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8 plateau at 500° C for 2 h to eliminate the organics. After sintering, each scaffold was
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10 placed in a plastic mold and a properly homogenized mixture of epoxy resin and hardener
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12 (WWAS and WWB4, Resineco-Green Composites, in a weight ratio 10:4) was poured
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14 into the mold at ambient temperature. Then, it was placed in a vacuum chamber at room
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16 temperature and a pressure of -0.1 MPa was applied for 10 hours to ensure the full
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18 impregnation of the scaffold. No further thermal treatment was necessary for
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20 consolidation of the composite. The same procedure was carried out using only the epoxy
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22 resin in order to compare its performance with that of the hybrid structure.
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36 **2.2. Mechanical testing**

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38 The fracture strength of the fabricated bioinspired material and that of the pure
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40 epoxy were measured in piston-on-three-ball biaxial tests. The results were compared to
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42 those reported in the literature for the commercial dental composites [5]. The specimens
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44 for biaxial bending tests were obtained by cutting (Accutom-50, Struers, Ballerup,
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46 Denmark) the impregnated scaffold parallel to the occlusal surface, as defined in Fig. 1.
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48 The specimens, of around 3 mm in thickness, were polished to a 1- μ m finish on the
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50 surface that was placed at the bottom (under tensile stress) during the biaxial bending
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52 test, in contact with the three supporting balls of 6.5 mm diameter. The same procedure
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54 was followed to obtain test specimens of pure epoxy. The load was applied by a hardened
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4 steel cylindrical piston at a crosshead speed of 6 mm/min. The bending strength (σ_B) was
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7 calculated using the following equation, proposed by Shetty et al. [20] based on the
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9 solution by Kirstein and Wooley [21]:

$$\sigma_B = \frac{3F}{4\pi} \cdot \frac{(x-y)}{t^2} \quad (1)$$

14 where

$$x = (1 + \nu) \text{Ln} \left(\frac{r_2}{r_3} \right)^2 + \left[\frac{1-\nu}{2} \right] \left(\frac{r_2}{r_3} \right)^2 \quad (2)$$

$$y = (1 + \nu) \left[1 + \text{Ln} \left(\frac{r_1}{r_3} \right)^2 \right] + (1 - \nu) \left(\frac{r_1}{r_3} \right)^2 \quad (3)$$

24 and F is the maximum force of the load-displacement curve, t is the thickness of the
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26 specimen, r_1 is the radius of the supporting circle (6.9 mm), r_2 is the radius of the piston
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28 (1.475 mm), r_3 is the sample radius (15.5 mm) and ν is the Poisson's ratio (assumed
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30 equal to 0.28 for the HAp-Epoxy composite).
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33 The wear behaviour of the bioinspired composite was also evaluated and
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35 compared with experimental results for the two selected commercial dental composites:
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37 Vita Enamic® and 3M™ Lava™ Ultimate. For this purpose, sliding-wear tests were
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39 conducted on all selected materials under a pin-on-disk configuration (THT1000, Anton
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41 Paar GmbH, Graz, Austria). A normal load of 30 N was applied using a mirror-finished
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43 zirconia (3Y-TZP) sphere of radius 3 mm, while the specimen was rotated with a linear
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45 sliding speed of 1 cm/s for a total sliding distance of 150 m, leaving a track of 2 mm
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47 radius. An artificial saliva solution (LACER S.A., Barcelona Spain) was used as
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49 lubricant. After the tests, the worn surface of each disk was characterized by optical
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51 profilometry (Profilm 3D, Filmetric, USA), optical microscopy (Epiphot 300, Nikon,
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53 Japan), and FE-SEM (QUANTA 3D FEG, FEI Company, Hillsboro, OR).
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7 **2.3 Microstructure analysis**
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9 Observations by field-emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM;
10 QUANTA 3D FEG, FEI Company, Hillsboro, OR) of polished and fractured surfaces
11 structures were carried out on gold-sputtered specimens. Thermogravimetric analyses
12 (SETSYS Evolution-16 SETARAM, France) were carried out on the bioinspired material
13 and the commercial dental composites to determine the ceramic content in each case.
14 Heating was carried out in air at a ramp of 10 °C/min up to a temperature of 900 °C.
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28 **3. Results and Discussion**
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30 **3.1. Microstructure**
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32 Robocasting (DIW) was proved to be a suitable AM technique for producing
33 biomimetic microstructures inspired by dental enamel. The high solid loading in the
34 robocasting inks allowed the fabrication of complex bioceramic structures with struts of a
35 high green density, which translated into low contractions and prevented microcracking
36 during sintering. Consequently, the fabricated structures reproduced with high fidelity the
37 CAD design: a porous network of cylindrical rods in a log-pile configuration that, after a
38 successful impregnation with an epoxy resin, yielded the desired biomimetic composite
39 materials. Figure 2 shows representative SEM micrographs of the microstructures of all
40 materials analyzed in this work. Figures 2a and 2b allow us to compare the
41 microstructures of the natural material (human dental enamel, occlusal surface) and the
42 bioinspired composite developed in this work. There are clear similarities, as well as
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4 some differences. The two microstructures consist of high aspect ratio mineral (HAp)
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6 rods, aligned perpendicular to the occlusal surface, and separated by a bonding phase.
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8 Interfaces appear largely free of defects/microcracks in both cases. The penetration of
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10 resin in the ceramic structure of the bioinspired material is satisfactory, due to the
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12 complete filling of the pores between rods. No evidence of residual porosity from trapped
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14 bubbles in the initial resin mixture can be observed in the polymeric phase. Regarding
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16 the ceramic mesh, it is noticeable that the rods shape is properly maintained after the
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18 fabrication process, albeit with a significant rod diameter reduction down to an average
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20 value of $270 \pm 20 \mu\text{m}$ after sintering, which is still significantly larger than the
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22 corresponding value in the natural material ($\sim 5 \mu\text{m}$). The rest of the parameters used in
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24 the printing model became also significantly smaller: $s_1 = 0.48 \pm 0.03 \text{ mm}$, $s_2 = 0.97 \pm$
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26 0.04 mm and $h = 0.19 \pm 0.01 \text{ mm}$. These rod separations are, obviously, much larger than
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28 in the natural enamel.
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37 As shown in Figure 2, the ceramic volumetric content in the commercial dental
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39 composites is closer to the enamel's, but their microstructures are fundamentally different
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41 from those of the natural and bioinspired materials. LavaTM Ultimate (Fig. 2c) consists of
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43 equiaxed ceramic particles of micrometric size embedded in a polymeric matrix.
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45 According to the manufacturer, the weight percentages of ceramic and polymer phase are
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47 80 wt% and 20 wt%, respectively. By contrast, in Enamic® (Fig. 2d) the polymer
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49 infiltrates a porous ceramic (feldspathic) preform. According to the manufacturer, and as
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51 verified in our own TGA measurements, the weight percentages of ceramic and polymer
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53 phase are 86 wt% and 14 wt%, respectively. As a result, the continuous phase is the
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55 polymer in LavaTM Ultimate and ceramic in Enamic®. In both cases, the interfaces
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4 between the polymer and ceramic phases are weak, which has been associated with a
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6 significantly lower sliding wear resistance compared to natural enamel [9]. Regarding the
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8 bioinspired composite, the TGA measurement reveals that its ceramic content is
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10 55.8 wt%, notably lower than that of the two commercial materials. Although in order to
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12 find differences in the mechanical behavior due only to the unique microstructural
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14 arrangement the ideal content of ceramic in the composition should have been greater,
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16 this lower concentration was selected to facilitate polymer infiltration and guarantee
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18 obtaining a well impregnated structure. Nonetheless, this is considered a minor limitation,
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20 since the purpose of this work is to evaluate the feasibility of this novel biomimetic
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22 material for dental applications as proof of concept, and to find out some preliminary
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24 guidelines that may contribute to optimize the proposed bioinspired design in the future.
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33 **3.2. Mechanical behaviour**

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35 The mechanical performance of the bioinspired composite was first evaluated
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37 through biaxial flexure testing. A representative load-displacement curve obtained during
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39 these tests is shown in Figure 3. Data obtained for pure epoxy is included for comparison.
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41 A clear linear elastic regime, with a significantly higher modulus than the pure polymer,
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43 is followed by a progressive reduction of the slope until a maximum in the applied force
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45 is reached. After this maximum, the load decreases in a gradual manner, albeit faster than
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47 for the pure polymer, even after large displacements. The elastoplastic behaviour and,
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49 especially, the capability of the structure to maintain its integrity and significant load-
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51 bearing capacity even at high elongations contrasts starkly with the brittle behaviour
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53 exhibited by the commercial materials (see inset in Fig. 3) where the fracture is
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4 catastrophic [22]. Thus, the mechanical behaviour of the bioinspired composite seems to
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6 be controlled mostly by the polymeric matrix at least for the material compositions
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8 (HAp/Epoxy) and ceramic content selected in this preliminary work. Indeed, the lack of
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10 load drops in the biaxial curve (Fig. 3) indicates that failure occurs progressively, not
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12 abruptly as would be expected if the ceramic phase was controlling the fracture behavior
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14 [23,24].
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19 The micrographs of the fracture surface in Figure 4 evidence that cracks
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21 propagate along the ceramic-polymer interphases, following a tortuous path as they are
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23 diverted by the vertical rods and cut irregularly through the section of the horizontal ones.
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25 Indeed, there is evidence of detachment of some rods from the polymeric matrix that
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27 indicates an interfacial adhesion with room for improvement. In particular, no
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29 microfibrils are observed at the detached interfaces unlike in previous reports on
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31 TCP/PCL structures [23, 25], indicating that the polymer is too brittle to produce them;
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33 although it is true that the residual microporosity in the current HAp rods is also much
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35 lower than in the cited study.
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41 The biomimetic material exhibits a biaxial strength, which provides a measure of
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43 resistance to single-cycle overloads, of 63 ± 4 MPa, which is somewhat lower than the
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45 values reported for the commercial dental composites (140 MPa and 225 MPa for VITA
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47 Enamic® and Lava™ Ultimate, respectively [5, 9]. Nevertheless, such differences do not
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49 seem unsurmountable given the biomimetic material developed in this study is just an
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51 unoptimized prototype intended to provide just a proof of concept for the proposed
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53 microarchitecture. Its weaker behavior is attributed to the dissimilarities in composition:
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55 the lower ceramic content in the structure compared to the commercial materials and the
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4 differences in the nature of the ceramic phase. Indeed, HAp is a much weaker ceramic
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6 material than the nanometric alumina, zirconia and silica particles used as fillers in the
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8 commercial composites. In fact, the strength of the bioinspired material is lower than the
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10 intrinsic biaxial strength of the polymer (74 ± 2 MPa), but this is not so surprising given
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12 that the majority of the ceramic rods were aligned perpendicular to the generated stresses
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14 and the low intrinsic strength of the chosen ceramic material. Only the elastic modulus
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16 was significantly enhanced over the bare polymer in the bioinspired composite.
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21 The performance of these bioinspired architectures seems to be controlled by the
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23 ceramic/polymer interface. The horizontally oriented rods, although few, can contribute
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25 to the reinforcement of the matrix, but their effect is insufficient to counteract the loss of
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27 strength produced by the introduction of the weaker interfaces. Delamination at the
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29 interphase would accelerate plastic deformation of the remaining continuous polymer and
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31 trigger the failure of the horizontal ceramic rods. Consequently, the adhesion strength
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33 between the polymer and the ceramic might be critical since such interfaces act as the
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35 weakest link in the microstructure. Consequently, improving the interfacial strength
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37 appears as a logical approach for optimizing the mechanical performance of the proposed
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39 bioinspired composites. In natural enamel, the interfacial energy is about one half that of
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41 bulk hydroxyapatite [10]. Introducing surface roughness or microporosity in the rods to
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43 facilitate polymer penetration and geometrical interlocking between both phases, or
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45 enhancing the chemical interaction between both phases through material selection and
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47 molecular grafting arise as promising alternatives in this regard. Although increasing the
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49 microporosity in the ceramic struts would reduce their intrinsic strength, upon the
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4 infiltration of the polymer such reduction will be greatly minimized due to the defect
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6 healing induced by the organic phase [26, 27].
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9 In the same way, the ceramic rods should be aligned with a pattern that make
10 them play a more active role in the load bearing capability, reducing their dependence on
11 the interphase quality. A possible approach would be to tilt and intertwine the vertical
12 rods mimicking the actual structure of the inorganic fibers in natural enamel to avoid
13 having all the weak interfaces unfavourably oriented. This would also enhance the
14 toughness of the bioinspired composite, as the crack path would become more tortuous.
15 Such strategy will also require, most probably, a reduction in the size of the struts and
16 their separation, bringing them closer to the natural microstructure. Reducing the size of
17 the rods would increase their intrinsic strength and subsequently the strength of the
18 hybrid structure. In addition, a reduction in the amount of inter-rod polymer would bring
19 their ceramic content and mechanical performance closer to the commercial materials,
20 thus enhancing the wear behavior and the rigidity of the bioinspired material as well as its
21 strength.
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41 In any case, the wear resistance, which is an indication of resistance to long-term
42 mechanical degradation, of the prototype bioinspired composite can already compete
43 with the commercial solutions. The steady-state coefficients of friction (CoF) recorded
44 during the wear tests are similar for the three materials: 0.12 ± 0.04 (Bioinspired), $0.10 \pm$
45 0.03 (Lava™ Ultimate), and 0.13 ± 0.04 (Enamic®). And, as shown in the representative
46 profilometry curves of Figure 5, the width and average depth of the surface scar are
47 comparable in the bioinspired material and Lava™ Ultimate, although both are
48 significantly greater than in Enamic®. The most notable difference between the
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4 bioinspired material and the commercial composites is that the profile of the wear track
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6 appears to be significantly more irregular in the former. This is attributed to the
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8 substantially coarser microstructure of the biomimetic composite.
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11 The specific wear rate (SWR) values calculated from dimensions of the wear
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13 scars at the end of the tests are $(7 \pm 2) \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ mm}^3/\text{Nm}$ (Bioinspired), $(4.0 \pm 0.2) \cdot 10^{-5}$
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15 mm^3/Nm (LavaTM Ultimate), and $(1.1 \pm 0.2) \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ mm}^3/\text{Nm}$ (Enamic®). These values
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17 indicate that under the current test conditions wear is severe in the LavaTM Ultimate and
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19 bioinspired materials, with SWRs within the same order of magnitude, and is at the
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21 boundary between mild and severe in Enamic®. The results obtained for the commercial
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23 composites here, under pin-on-disk, are qualitatively consistent with results obtained in
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25 an earlier study, under a ball-on-three-disk configuration, that also indicated a higher
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27 wear resistance in Enamic® [5].
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34 Figure 6 shows high magnification SEM micrographs representative of the wear
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36 damage in the materials. In all cases, wear takes place by abrasion. In the bioinspired
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38 material (Figs. 6A, B), the abrasive agents are mainly micron and sub-micron sized
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40 fragments (third body particulates) dislodged from the HAp rods. However, despite the
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42 material removal from the surface, there is no wholesale pull out of rods and the bonding
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44 phase remains, for the most part, in place. The smallest sub-micron particles result in
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46 microcontacts below the threshold load for macro-fracture (*i.e.*, sub-threshold). These
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48 limit material removal to the region immediately below the surface by coalescence of
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50 microcracks and some plastic deformation, thus preventing the pull-out of rods and
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52 bonding phase, much as in natural enamel [9]. The largest particles result in localized,
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54 post-threshold microcontacts that can cause deeper material removal. As a result, the
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4 bioinspired material shows severe wear but, remarkably, its wear resistance is comparable
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6 to the commercial composites despite its substantially lower mineral content. This is
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8 especially true in the case of Lava Ultimate where plastic deformation of the relatively
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10 soft, continuous polymer matrix results in plastic deformation of the composite, as
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12 evidenced by the presence of large grooves, parallel to the sliding direction, inside its
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14 wear track (Figs. 6C and 6D). Moreover, reinforcing ceramic particles are easily removed
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16 wholesale from the matrix in this case, producing hard and large (micrometer-sized)
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18 third-body abrasives which result in post-threshold micro contacts and severe wear [28,
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20 29]. On the contrary, in Enamic® the connected phase is the relatively hard ceramic,
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22 which is more resistant to deformation. Thus, the Enamic® material shows mostly
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24 removal of the polymeric phase that infiltrates the connected ceramic preform (Fig. 6E).
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26 The latter remains largely intact, as seen at higher magnifications (Fig. 6F). As a result,
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28 third bodies in Enamic® are softer than those in the biomimetic material and Lava™
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30 Ultimate and, thus, are more likely to produce sub-threshold microcontacts, which
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32 explains the much milder wear [28, 29].
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42 The above discussion reveals that the nature of the connected phase is a key
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44 microstructural element in two-phase dental materials: the harder ceramic phase should
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46 be continuous for improved wear resistance. However, having a continuous polymeric
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48 matrix enhances toughness and makes the materials more tolerant to flaws and damage.
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50 The proposed biomimetic material provides a solution to this conundrum, since the
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52 organic and inorganic phases are co-continuous. Indeed, transverse rods join the vertical
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54 ones into a continuous network or ceramic skeleton that partly compensates for the larger
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4 separation between rods compared to natural enamel, by preventing pull out of the
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6 vertical rods and hampering buckling.
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9 Besides, it is worth mentioning that the versatile process used for the fabrication
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11 of these bioinspired composites, robocasting plus polymer impregnation, should facilitate
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13 the incorporation of additives in both the organic and the inorganic phases in order to
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15 tailor the optical properties of the composite with the aim of closely matching the
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17 aesthetics of natural teeth.
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21 Despite the advantages of the proposed bioinspired architecture and the
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23 competitive results obtained, the prototype fabricated in this work, while serving as a
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25 proof of concept, still has ample room for improvement. Firstly, material selection should
26
27 be optimized: while HAp has obvious advantages in terms of biocompatibility and is the
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29 material found in natural enamel, the artificial robocast material is probably too weak for
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31 this application. Its low strength and toughness are probably responsible for the removal
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33 of the larger abrasive particles from the vertical rods during the wear tests, resulting in
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35 severe damage. Substitution by other ceramic compositions, like silica glass or alumina,
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37 conventionally used in commercial dental composites, seems to be an obvious first step.
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39 Optimization of the design should also be addressed making use of the extraordinary
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41 flexibility and versatility that robocasting and other additive manufacturing techniques
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43 can provide. In particular, efforts should be devoted to reducing rod size and separation
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45 that, as already discussed, will lead to significant improvements in the mechanical
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47 performance of the bioinspired composites [30]. Moreover, the rod architecture can also
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49 be adjusted to maximize strength and toughness. Exploring structures with graded
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51 mineral content and printing decussation patterns near the enamel/dentin junction [17]
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4 appear as promising strategies, since they would replicate the structural features
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6 responsible for the outstanding toughness of natural enamel [10].
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10 11 **4. Conclusions** 12

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14 The present study demonstrates the suitability of the robocasting technique,
15 followed by polymer infiltration, for the fabrication of co-continuous ceramic/polymer
16 dental composites inspired on the microstructure of human enamel. Robocasting, as other
17 additive manufacturing techniques, can produce interconnected networks of ceramic rods
18 aligned perpendicular to the occlusal surface mimicking the natural material. The
19 prototype composite produced in this study as a proof of concept, consisting of co-
20 continuous HAp and epoxy networks, has demonstrated already a mechanical
21 performance remarkably close to existing commercial solutions, both in terms of **biaxial**
22 **strength (63 ± 4 MPa)** and wear resistance (**SWR of $(7 \pm 2) \cdot 10^{-5}$ mm³/Nm**). Since the
23 produced material is far from optimized and the ceramic content attained was
24 significantly lower than those of the commercial composites, the results of this work
25 confirm the proposed strategy as a very promising alternative for the production of novel
26 dental composites with enhanced mechanical performance.
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31 **Figure Captions**

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33 Figure 1. Scaffold design used for direct ink writing.
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36 Figure 2. SEM micrographs representative of the occlusal surface of (A) human dental
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38 enamel and (B) the bioinspired composite developed in this work. Commercial dental
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40 composites are included for comparison: (C) LavaTM Ultimate imaged using secondary
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42 electrons and (D) Vita Enamic[®] imaged using backscattered electrons to enhance
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44 contrast between the organic and inorganic phases. Images (A) and (D) taken from [9].
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48 Figure 3. Representative load-displacement curves obtained during biaxial bending tests
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50 performed on the developed bioinspired composites (blue line) and pure epoxy specimens
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52 (green line). Reported biaxial curves [22] for the commercial dental composites are
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54 included as an inset for comparison (Vita Enamic[®] in red and Lava UltimateTM in
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56 orange).
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Figure 4. Representative SEM micrographs of fractured bioinspired composite after biaxial flexure testing showing (A) the fracture surface and (B) the crack path along the bottom surface of the biaxial specimen.

Figure 5. Representative profilometry curves showing the width and depth of wear tracks produced after pin-on-disk tests performed on the bioinspired composite (blue line), and the two commercial composites: Lava™ Ultimate (orange) and Vita Enamic® (red).

Optical images displayed on the right show the path followed during the profilometry scans on each material.

Figure 6. SEM micrographs of representative wear tracks at the end of the pin-on-disk tests performed on (A, B) the bioinspired composite, (C, D) Lava™ Ultimate and (E,F) Vita Enamic®.

